

Decay Heat Prediction of Spent Nuclear Fuels Using kNN Regression

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ABSTRACT

Accurate prediction of decay heat in spent nuclear fuel is crucial for the safe operation of nuclear storage. This study presents a comparative machine learning-based analysis of MOX and UOX fuels using a large-scale Serpent2 dataset. A k -nearest neighbors (kNN) model is employed to predict total decay heat from non-destructive assay-accessible features, with uncertainty calibration and feature importance evaluation. We demonstrate that UOX predictions rely predominantly on ^{137}Cs activity, while MOX fuels require broader isotopic information, including actinide indicators and historical parameters such as the initial fuel composition. The results support the deployment of tailored, interpretable prediction models for decay heat evaluation.

Keywords: Spent nuclear fuel; decay heat; machine learning; k -nearest neighbors; MOX fuel; UOX fuel; uncertainty quantification; non-destructive assay methods

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate characterization of spent nuclear fuel (SNF) is essential for safe waste management and repository performance assessment [1]. One of the most limiting physical observables is decay heat, which represents the residual thermal power emitted after reactor shutdown and impacts the design and layout of SNF storage.

Uranium Oxide (UOX) and Mixed Oxide (MOX) fuels represent two classes of SNF with fundamentally different fissile input vectors and irradiation behavior. UOX is the most commonly used fuel worldwide, enriched in ^{235}U , and accumulates fission products and minor actinides during irradiation. MOX fuel, on the other hand, is produced from recycled spent fuel or weapons-grade plutonium, resulting in a mixture mainly of ^{239}Pu , ^{240}Pu , ^{241}Pu , ^{242}Pu , and depleted uranium, leading to enhanced actinide buildup. As a consequence, the post-irradiation isotopic inventory of MOX fuels is more diverse and is more strongly influenced by spontaneous-fission sources and higher alpha-emitting actinide buildup.

Non-destructive assay (NDA) methods for SNF characterization typically rely on accessible, passive measurements, such as gamma spectrometry and neutron counting, which provide limited and indirect information on properties of interest, such as decay heat or nuclide inventory. These measurements could be performed by operators of geological repositories of SNF; thus, it is important to have a fast and reliable method to connect measurable signals with decay heat. Traditional methods, such as high-fidelity Monte Carlo depletion codes, often require extensive input data and are computationally demanding [2].

In contrast, data-driven approaches can use large precomputed simulation databases to build fast, accurate surrogates that operate on limited inputs [3]. Solans *et al.* have previously demonstrated

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that the decay heat of UOX spent nuclear fuel can be reliably estimated using non-destructive assay (NDA) signatures, particularly via gamma spectroscopy and neutron coincidence measurements [3, 4]. Their approach highlighted the predictive potential of passive data, paving the way for more accessible decay heat diagnostics; however, it lacked a study of MOX fuel types. The present work builds upon these findings by extending the methodology with an interpretable and uncertainty-aware machine learning framework, specifically a k -nearest neighbors (kNN) regression method [5], instead of the Gaussian process used by Solans *et al.* Its main advantage is scalability: Gaussian-process regression typically requires $\mathcal{O}(N^3)$ training cost in standard implementations, whereas kNN has no global training step and its inference cost scales approximately as $\mathcal{O}(N)$ per query, making it practical for large simulation libraries.

The prediction model uses any information realistically available, such as features accessible via NDA (gamma-emitter activities and neutron count rates), and fuel-history data of the SNF. The relevance of each feature for the predictions is evaluated through feature-importance analysis. The model is trained on a large-scale dataset generated using the Serpent2 Monte Carlo burnup code, using a 2D pin-cell model [6]. This dataset covers a wide range of initial enrichments (IE)*, burn-ups (BU), and cooling times (CT). It includes over 1.3 million labeled entries, making it suitable for realistic scenario modeling. In this work, we focus on fuel rods with long cooling times (CT > 10 years), relevant for regular waste management.

*Initial Fissile Content (IFC) for MOX fuels, defined as the relative content of a fixed plutonium vector; see [6] for details. Varying the Pu vector may change actinide buildup and the mapping from NDA-accessible features to decay heat, but is not considered in this paper.

2. DECAY HEAT CONTRIBUTIONS

Decay heat arises primarily from beta and gamma decays of fission products and alpha decays of actinides from actinide buildup. The relative contributions vary strongly with fuel type and cooling time. Figure 1 highlights these differences: the decay heat of spent UOX fuel after 10 years of cooling is dominated by long-lived fission products such as ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr , with the gradual ingrowth of ^{241}Am from actinide buildup. MOX fuel, in contrast, exhibits substantial actinide contributions already at early cooling times (e.g. ^{244}Cm , ^{241}Am , ^{238}Pu).

Figure 1. Relative isotopic decay heat contributions for UOX and MOX fuels over cooling time. The ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library was used to calculate the decay heat of each isotope, and SNF with a wide range of IE and BU values were averaged to give a broad picture of the decay heat composition throughout the fuel library. $^{137}\text{Cs}/^{137\text{m}}\text{Ba}$ and $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ are reported as combined contributions.

3. METHODOLOGY

The decay heat predictions were carried out using a customized k -nearest neighbors (kNN) regression framework tailored to realistic non-destructive assay (NDA) conditions. The methodology balances predictive accuracy, interpretability, and uncertainty quantification across a heterogeneous fuel dataset. The dataset was pre-filtered to contain only SNFs with a cooling time of at least 3 years, for relevance. We chose the following features as prediction-model inputs.

- **Activity of ^{137}Cs , ^{134}Cs and ^{154}Eu :** The decay of these isotopes results in strong γ -lines, and they are large contributors to decay heat. They are abundant and expected to be detectable for fuels with intermediate CT, as they have relatively long half-lives.
- **Count rate of spontaneous fission (TOT_SF):** Used in this study to approximate the measured total neutron count rate, since the multiplicity can be assumed to be fairly constant, under the assumption that the (α, n) contribution is significantly lower. This has been shown for both UOX and MOX fuels with similar characteristics, except for UOX at BU around 10 MWd/kg-U [7, 8]. This feature provides information on actinide buildup.
- **Initial enrichment (IE):** For SNF with a known history, it is reasonable to assume that the initial composition is known with high precision. It can be useful for predicting the actinide contribution to decay heat. For safeguards applications, or for SNF with unknown history, however, we cannot rely on this feature.
- **Cooling time (CT):** Since relative isotopic contributions change with cooling time, CT is also useful for improving prediction accuracy. This parameter is also reasonable to be known with high precision, except in safeguards applications.

All input features were standardized to have zero mean and unit variance before model training to avoid biases due to the choice of units and to increase prediction efficiency. The dataset was resampled such that decay heat follows an approximately uniform distribution, so the metrics are not biased toward low-decay-heat events, which are overrepresented in the original dataset. The dataset was split randomly into a training (80%), a calibration (10%), and a test (10%) set. For computational efficiency, a smaller set with 10 000 samples was randomly drawn from the calibration set for evaluating the different metrics of the model, for uncertainty calibration, and hyperparameter tuning. The test set was then used to obtain unbiased predictions on unseen data.

To simulate measurement errors, normally distributed relative noise was added to each feature in a range of 0–5%, in accordance with realistic uncertainties of experimental measurements [9, 10]. In the case of the CT and IE features, the purpose of the noise level is to obtain conservative uncertainty estimates.

Whenever a prediction was made, for each target sample, a number k of nearest neighbors were selected. The prediction was then computed as a weighted average of the k neighbors, with weights inversely proportional to the Minkowski distance in the normalized parameter space. The hyperparameters $k = 15$ and $\alpha = 2$ were chosen by the authors, as they were among the better-performing combinations for both fuel types, and they were preferred for the sake of interpretability and simplicity*.

*Because of the uniformity of the simulated SNF library, the value of k and the order of the Minkowski-distance metric (α , where $\alpha = 1$ is the Manhattan and $\alpha = 2$ is the Euclidean metric) had only a very small effect on prediction performance. A grid search for optimal values was conducted over $8 < k < 50$ and $0.4 < \alpha < 4$ for both fuel types, and the performance was relatively flat, with a relative difference of $< 10\%$ between the best and worst combinations for both UOX and MOX.

For each input x , the model outputs a prediction $y_{\text{pred}}(x)$ and an uncalibrated uncertainty $u(x)$ (with $u(x) \equiv \sigma_{NN}(x)$, the standard deviation of the k nearest neighbors). With $y_{\text{true}}(x)$ we define the residual $r(x) = y_{\text{true}}(x) - y_{\text{pred}}(x)$. On a calibration, we assess the residual spread with respect to $u(x)$ by grouping samples with similar $u(x)$ (binning). If $u(x)$ were an ideal estimator of the uncertainty, then $\text{Std}(r(x) \mid u(x) \approx u') \approx u'$ for any u' . Empirically, we observe an approximately linear trend instead:

$$\text{Std}(r(x) \mid u(x) \approx u') \simeq a + b u'. \quad (1)$$

For the noise levels studied here, we typically obtain $a \approx 0$ and 0.1 (unperturbed) $< b < 0.9$ (5% noise level). The relation can be understood as follows: for an unperturbed test point in a uniformly filled training space, predictions are much closer to the truth than σ_{NN} suggests, indicating that the systematic uncertainties are overestimated. When additional statistical noise is introduced, b increases significantly. We therefore define the calibrated uncertainty as

$$\delta_{\text{est}}(x) = a + b u(x), \quad (2)$$

and we validate the fitted parameters (a, b) on an unseen test set.

In Section 6, we study the influence of input features on prediction accuracy. Two importance metrics were computed:

- **Permutation importance:** For the selected feature, we randomly permute its values among all samples. Instead of the actual signal, a random value is used from the same distribution, and the increase in the mean magnitude of the relative error (MRE) is measured. This metric indicates the model's sensitivity to that feature and thus whether it carries useful predictive information.
- **Masking importance:** We completely omit the selected feature and then measure the increase in MRE. This metric indicates whether the signal carried by the selected feature is unique or redundant, i.e., whether it is actually necessary for prediction.

4. FEATURE CORRELATIONS

Figure 2. Pearson correlation coefficients between selected features and total decay heat over cooling time for UOX fuel (left) and MOX fuel (right), calculated on the entire simulated SNF library. Gaussian noise was added to all features, corresponding to 1% of each feature's standard deviation across the dataset, to suppress purely mathematical correlations for effectively decayed nuclides.

We first assessed the linear relationships between the available features and the total decay heat. Figure 2 shows the Pearson correlation coefficients between the model inputs and decay heat, binned by cooling time, for MOX and UOX fuels. Pearson coefficients here quantify linear covariation within the simulated library; they should not be interpreted as direct rankings of physical contributions to decay heat.

For both fuel types, ^{137}Cs shows strong correlation with decay heat over a wide time range, especially in the intermediate cooling regime (10–40 years). For UOX fuel, the decay heat remains closely tied to fission products like ^{137}Cs , ^{134}Cs , and ^{154}Eu , as we would expect from earlier studies [11]. For MOX, these fission products are relevant at short cooling times, but their correlation weakens beyond ~ 30 years due to increasing dominance of actinide decay. Accordingly, IE shows a higher correlation in MOX at later times, consistent with the longer half-lives of built-up actinides from irradiation.

5. PREDICTION ACCURACY AND UNCERTAINTY CALIBRATION

Figures 3 and 4 illustrate the prediction performance and uncertainty calibration (described in Section 3) for both fuel types. Each model was evaluated on test sets using standard kNN regression with calibrated residual-based uncertainty estimates (δ_{est} , defined by Eq. (2)).

Figure 3. The left panel shows predicted versus true decay heat for the test set, while the inset shows the residual distribution. The middle panels show the spread of the residuals within bins of similar uncalibrated uncertainty $u(x)$, as a function of $u(x)$, for calibration and validation purposes (see Section 3). The right panels show the mean relative residual within the same bins and serve to identify potential systematic biases in the predictions.

UOX predictions show good agreement with ground truth, with a mean MRE (Magnitude of Relative Error) of 3.1%, even at 5% perturbed noise. MOX predictions exhibit even greater performance (mean MRE = 2.6%), which reflects the reliance on more input channels for prediction (see Section 6).

For comparison, Solans *et al.* reported a mean MRE = 4.6% at the same 5% rate of artificial noise, when they used gamma and neutron measurements for UOX fuel prediction using a different machine learning method, the Gaussian process [4].

Figure 4. Prediction performance (left), uncertainty calibration (middle), and bias validation (right) for MOX fuel.

6. FEATURE IMPORTANCE

We use permutation importance to discuss the predictive usefulness of features, and masking importance to discuss their uniqueness, as defined in Section 3.

Figure 5. Feature importances for UOX fuel (top) and MOX fuel (bottom) to quantify the significance of each feature for the decay heat predictions. The performance degradation is measured in percentage points.

Figure 5 shows the resulting importance factors for UOX and MOX fuels, with 5% perturbed noise added to the test set. For UOX, ^{137}Cs dominates both importance metrics, followed by the spontaneous-fission count rate and ^{134}Cs . While the permutation importance of ^{154}Eu is also relatively high, its masking importance is low, indicating that the information it carries is largely redundant. If we reduce the input feature set to ^{137}Cs , TOT_SF, and ^{134}Cs , we obtain a mean MRE of 4.8% at the 5% artificial-noise level, similar to what was found in Solans *et al.* [4].

MOX fuel shows more complex behavior. While ^{137}Cs has high permutation importance, its masking importance is surprisingly low. Initial fissile content becomes dominant in terms of masking importance, indicating that when IFC is unknown, prediction performance degrades substantially more for MOX than for UOX. For safeguards applications, this suggests that more sophisticated neutron measurements are needed to recover information on the fissile content of the SNF. In addition, permutation importance is relatively even across features, meaning that reliance on multiple channels yields more robust decay-heat predictions against input noise than for UOX, as shown in the next section. If we reduce the input feature set to IFC, TOT_SF, and ^{134}Cs , we obtain a mean MRE of 3.0% at the 5% artificial-noise level, only slightly worse than with all inputs.

7. UNCERTAINTY PROPAGATION STUDY

A controlled uncertainty propagation study was conducted by injecting Gaussian noise into input features across increasing amplitudes, with the same σ of 0% to 5% of the standard deviation for all input data, so it is independent of scaling. The aim was to quantify model robustness to imprecision in NDA measurements or uncertainties in the historical data.

Figure 6. Propagation of input noise in UOX (left) and MOX (right) fuel predictions. The MRE density distribution is shown using a violin plot, while the mean MRE is written out as a label.

Figure 6 shows the response of prediction error under increasing noise. For UOX, model performance degrades roughly at the same rate as noise is added, consistent with decay heat being largely determined by ^{137}Cs gamma activity. For MOX, we observe a lower, non-linear sensitivity to the noise level, consistent with our earlier findings that the prediction relies on multiple channels (especially IFC, TOT_SF, and ^{134}Cs), such that noise in any single feature has a smaller impact on the output.

8. CONCLUSION

This study presents a comparative, data-driven analysis of MOX and UOX spent nuclear fuel decay heat using interpretable machine learning. The simulation-derived dataset includes over 1.3 million unique samples across diverse fuel histories, with realistic isotopic inventories and detector-accessible observables. We show that decay heat prediction is accurate and robust for both fuel types using kNN regression. Uncertainty quantification and perturbation studies demonstrate that UOX predictions are highly reliant on the measurement of ^{137}Cs activity. In contrast, MOX models are more resilient to input noise as they rely on more independent channels, but they are also highly sensitive to missing fuel-history data.

In future work, we intend to combine gamma-spectroscopic measurements with neutron-neutron coincidences to better predict the actinide decay-heat component and the criticality of SNF, while benchmarking against experimental data is also being prepared. The effect of realistic variations in the plutonium vector of MOX fuels will also be studied.

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